

**Designing a Roadmap for
Effective and Sustainable Strategies for
Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of
EU Agriculture to Navigate within a
Safe and Just Operating Space**

**Spatio-Temporal Patterns of
Field Structural Change and
Related Farm Developments**

Working Paper

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1 Spatio-Temporal Patterns of Field Structural Change and Related Farm
2 Developments

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11

12 **ABSTRACT**

13 Understanding how the structures of agricultural fields change over time can provide valuable
14 insights into the impacts of institutional and infrastructural changes, farmers' economic
15 decisions, or natural conditions on the landscape. Existing studies provide evidence of field
16 structural change from small case studies over extended periods. While valuable for detailed
17 site-specific insights, generalizations from single or a few case study sites are prone to omission
18 of heterogeneity from excluded relevant areas, thereby inaccurately capturing the condition in
19 larger regions of interest. We conduct a large-scale spatial analysis of field structural change in
20 Lower Saxony, Germany, to understand the pattern of change in field size, shape, and density
21 in every agriculturally productive 10 km² area of the study area. We relate these changes to the
22 changes in farm size and number of farms in the districts of Lower Saxony. Our results show
23 that field structural changes vary between areas and districts, but within eastern or western sides
24 of the study area, most areas and districts exhibit a similar direction of change. The relationship
25 between observed heterogeneous changes in field structure and changes in farm structure differs
26 depending on whether districts mainly cultivate cereals, forage crops, or grasslands. These
27 varied results suggest the need for differentiated strategies for improving the effectiveness and
28 targeting of landscape sustainability policies. Efforts to change fields and landscape outcomes

29 through farm-level structural changes might need to pay attention to not just farm size but to
30 differentiation arising from main cultivated crops.

31

32 **Abbreviations:** European Union (EU), European Green Deal (EGD), Common Agricultural
33 Policy (CAP), Field Structural Change (FiSC), Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
34 (NUTS), Landesamt für Bergbau, Energie und Geologie (LBEG), Integrated Administration
35 and Control System (IACS), fields per hectare of agricultural area (FA^{-1}), perimeter-area ratio
36 (SHAPE), median size of fields (MedFS), median perimeter (MedPeri), median field shape
37 metric (MedSHAPE), Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research
38 Foundation), Excellence Strategy (EXC)

39

40 **Keywords (2-7):** Agricultural Landscape, Agricultural Field, Structural Change, Panel Data,
41 Spatio-Temporal Analysis

42 **1. INTRODUCTION**

43 Agricultural land use and the structure of agricultural fields are crucial components of
44 agricultural production that shape the composition and configuration of landscapes, and
45 contribute to ecological outcomes, particularly biodiversity (Noack et al., 2022; Tschardt et
46 al., 2021). Existing studies such as Batáry et al. (2017), Gayer et al. (2019) and Noack et al.
47 (2022) show in cross-sectional comparison that differences in field structure are important for
48 biodiversity outcomes. Despite this recognized ecological relevance of field structures, the
49 central role of fields in agricultural production, and the frequency with which farmers change
50 field structures to meet economic and institutional requirements, the existing temporal
51 understanding of how field structures have changed is limited to a few regional and small-
52 location case studies. Furthermore, the existing studies cover long time spans, omitting
53 evidence from medium-term or more recent periods.

54 The literature on the economics, management, and outcomes of farms indicates a close
55 association between field structures and aspects of farm structure, such as the farm size (Clough
56 et al., 2020). In fact, there is evidence of a positive correlation between field size and farm size
57 (Jänicke et al., 2024; Levin, 2006). The literature links field shapes to farm structure and
58 management decisions, showing that large, regularly shaped fields are considered more
59 efficient than small, irregularly shaped fields for the use of large machinery (Janulevičius &
60 Čiplienė, 2018; Valtiala et al., 2023), which is typical of large farms. These farm-field linkages
61 suggest that changes in field structure, which are notably associated with ecological outcomes,
62 may also be associated with changes in farm structure. However, empirical evidence of the
63 degree of this relationship between farm and field structural changes is currently lacking.

64 This study aims to bridge the existing gaps by providing evidence on how field structures have
65 recently changed and how these changes relate to farm structural change. Specifically, we
66 address two research questions (RQs). First, what is the pattern of recent developments in field
67 structural change and, how do the patterns of field structural change compare spatially? Second,

68 how do the heterogeneous patterns of field structural change relate to farm structural change?
69 We investigate these questions across in a case study for Lower Saxony over 13 years and, as
70 such, provide spatially and temporally heterogeneous evidence of changes in field structures
71 and the relation to farm structural change in the German federal state. In this study, a field refers
72 to each unit of agricultural land managed or cultivated by a farm for a single cropping purpose.
73 This individual crop unit differs from the associated land term, parcel, which refers to the
74 administratively recognized land ownership unit. A parcel owned by a farm could be used for
75 one or more fields and a field could sit on one or more parcels. Following Aladesuru et al.
76 (2024), we use the term Field Structural Change (FiSC) to refer to changes in the size, shape,
77 and density of agricultural fields within defined landscape boundaries. FiSC is related to, but
78 differs from, the concept of land fragmentation or consolidation. While land fragmentation or
79 consolidation addresses changes in land structure at the parcel level, FiSC examines changes in
80 the structure of the fields, independent of their parcel identity.

81 The few existing studies on temporal FiSC provide valuable evidence but often consider small
82 local case studies that are not necessarily representative of larger areas of interest. These studies
83 offer detailed insights into site-specific dynamics, which, when extrapolated to conclusions for
84 larger areas, introduce the risk of omitting useful localized variations (Skaloš et al., 2012). In
85 the United States, Brown and Schulte (2011) selected one small town each from three
86 physiographic regions of interest in Iowa to compare how values of average patch size
87 (reflecting field size), shape index, and number of patches changed between 1937 and 2002.
88 While focusing mainly on land-use change in Saxony-Anhalt, Germany, Baessler & Klotz
89 (2006) studied a 4 km² site and examined changes in the number of fields, mean patch size, and
90 field shape complexity between 1953 and 2000. Lastly, the study sites used by Skaloš et al.
91 (2012) to assess field structure changes in Eastern Bohemia and Southern Sweden covered 244
92 ha and 321 ha, respectively.

93 This use of limited spatial premises in the existing studies, i.e., a 4 km² site or one small town
94 as cases studies, is often associated with data limitations, such as the use of aerial photographs
95 (Brown & Schulte, 2011; Skaloš et al., 2012), which pose labour- and time-intensive
96 digitization procedures with increasing demands as coverage expands. Given these limitations,
97 even though these existing studies span long time periods and aim to study larger regions of
98 interest, practicality requires not studying each year and site in the target regions, but rather a
99 calculated selection of seminal years and sites within the target time spans and regions. In recent
100 times, however, large-scale digitized spatial data sets have become increasingly available,
101 providing new opportunities to answer similarly spatially inclined questions and improve the
102 methodologies for old yet relevant questions (Leonhardt et al., 2024).

103 Answering the research questions posed in this study and providing an understanding of how
104 field structures change over time, while also delineating or associating with changes in farm
105 structure, contributes importantly to efforts for improving the sustainability implications of
106 agricultural landscape management processes. Although shorter than the time span covered in
107 prior studies, this study's examination of changes in agricultural fields over 13 years provides
108 a medium-term, spatially explicit perspective on the recent development of FiSC. This evidence
109 from all districts of Lower Saxony may reflect how fields have changed in possible relation to
110 European Union (EU) agricultural policies that directly or indirectly motivate FiSC, such as
111 subsidies that reward farmers for limiting field sizes to a certain threshold (RECHT.NRW.DE,
112 2022). The evidence from this study could therefore make valuable contribution to agricultural
113 policy discussions surrounding changes in field and farm sizes. For the Common Agricultural
114 Policy of the EU (EU CAP), it could contribute to discussion on changes in sizes of specific
115 field types (e.g., grasslands) and whether payments to large farms should be capped if these
116 farms are engaging in environmentally-beneficial land management practices (Matthews, 2019;
117 Petsakos et al., 2023), such as creating smaller fields which are considered beneficial from a
118 diversity perspective. Evidence on field structural change relationship with farm structural

119 change can inform policymakers about how changes in farm size may or may not infer changes
120 in field sizes and consequently biodiversity.

121 The remainder of this paper provides a detailed description of the data and methods applied in
122 the study in Section 2, a description of the results for the three posed research questions in
123 Section 3, further discussion pertaining to the study results according to the sequence of
124 research questions in Section 4, and concluding remarks in Section 5.

125 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

126 **2.1. Study area**

127 The study area of this study is the federal state of Lower Saxony, Germany. Lower Saxony
128 occupies over 47,000 km² of total land area in the northwest of Germany and uses
129 approximately 58% of its land area as agricultural land (Federal Statistical Office of Germany,
130 2024); as such it is the Federal state with the second-largest agricultural area in Germany. In
131 Lower Saxony, the number of farms has decreased over time across all farm size groups but the
132 total utilized agricultural area (UAA) has increased (Landesamt für Statistik Niedersachsen,
133 2025). Similar to other western states in Germany (Jänicke et al., 2024), field and farm sizes
134 are smaller in Lower Saxony than in neighboring states on the eastern side of Germany. Jänicke
135 et al. (2024) reported an average field size of 2.9 ha in the state in 2018, and an average farm
136 size of 55 ha. 73% of the agricultural land is used as arable land for cereals and forage crops,
137 27% as grassland and the rest for orchards and tree nurseries (Landesamt für Statistik
138 Niedersachsen, 2025). With predominant cultivation of grassland and forage crops for animal
139 production in the north and cereal production in the south (Figure 1), the state contributes at
140 large to animal husbandry and crop production in Germany.

141

142 *Figure 1: Study area map of Lower Saxony showing the district divisions of the state and the*
 143 *main cultivation type occupying the largest land area in each district.*

144 **2.2. Data**

145 *Field dataset*

146 We employ a 13-year vector geospatial dataset from the Land Parcel Identification System
 147 (LPIS) component of the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) (Leonhardt et
 148 al. 2024). For Lower Saxony, this IACS data is obtainable from the Lower Saxony Centre for
 149 Rural Development and Agricultural Promotion (*“Servicezentrum Landentwicklung und*
 150 *Agrarförderung”*). The IACS manages data related to the CAP payments, which requires
 151 beneficiary farmers to provide information about cultivated hectares of land (Leonhardt et al.,
 152 2024; Lomba et al., 2017). This data provides information about the spatial location of fields,
 153 and crucially for this study precise details about the shape of each field. We work with data
 154 from 2012 to 2024. The raw dataset for the study contains 11,762,466 records of agricultural
 155 fields with a yearly average of approximately 905,000 fields and a declining pattern relative to

156 the first year (2012). For our analysis, we drop very small geometries (below 100 m²),
157 constituting approximately 0.13% of fields in the data, we motivate this exclusion to focus our
158 analysis on actual fields used for production, excluding smaller reported geometries in corners
159 or in between fields. This results in 11,746,748 remaining fields covering an average of 2.57
160 million hectares each year. After dropping very small geometries, the average field size in the
161 study is 2.85 ha, and the maximum is 415.89 ha.

162 *Farm dataset*

163 To obtain information about farm structural change, we use agricultural structure datasets for
164 2010, 2016, and 2020, which are obtainable from the Lower Saxony statistics office. The
165 datasets provide values for the number of farms and total UAA for each of the 45 districts
166 (NUTS3 regions) in Lower Saxony. This comprises 37 rural districts (“*Landkreise*”) and 8
167 independent cities (“*Kreisfreie Städte*”). On average, the 45 districts comprise approximately
168 2.58 million hectares of utilized agricultural area, with about 37,624 farms per year. From this
169 available district farm data, we calculate the average farm UAA i.e., mean farm size by dividing
170 total UAA by the number of farms for each district. We then use these values of the number of
171 farms and mean farm size to associate FiSC with farm structural change.

172 *Spatial units and extent of Analysis*

173 A challenge to analysing FiSC patterns is tracking changes occurring to a field over time, since
174 FiSC can involve processes of field removal, addition, size expansion, or reduction. Thus, our
175 analysis proceeds at the level of defined spatial units rather than at the individual field level.
176 The spatial units used are the 10 km² reference grid of Germany, provided by the European
177 Environment Agency (EEA, 2013). To identify the district relevant to each cell of the grid, we
178 obtain data on administrative boundaries of Lower Saxony from the website of the state’s office
179 for geoinformation and state surveying (LGLN, n.d.), and perform a spatial join between the
180 grid and administrative boundaries to match each cell with its corresponding district. In case a
181 cell intersects more than one district, the cell belongs to the district with the largest overlap.

182 We spatially overlay the field dataset with the processed grid to examine changes in the fields
183 within every 10 km² area of the districts in Lower Saxony. This spatial mapping of fields to
184 grid cells localizes 568 to 570 cells to Lower Saxony, depending on the extent of each year's
185 field data. The cell with the most fields contains 4301 fields and, on average, a cell contains
186 1589 fields.

187 We focus our analysis on the districts with a relevant amount of agricultural activity and exclude
188 cells in the coastal areas of Weser-Ems and Lüneburg. Although included in the administrative
189 boundaries data, these areas are also not included among the 45 districts in the farm dataset.
190 Additionally, we exclude from further analysis cells that contain fewer than 300 fields across
191 all 13 years. Due to the relatively low number of fields in these cells, including them can easily
192 lead to extreme outliers, which can overshadow evidence from the cells that are more relevant
193 to agricultural production. Based on these conditions, 67 cells were removed in 2012, 2013,
194 2015, 2021 and 2024, 69 cells were removed in 2019 and 2020, whereas 68 cells were removed
195 in the remaining years. These eliminations balanced the field data to 501 cells for all years and
196 changed the average number of fields in a cell to 1775 fields.

197 **2.3. Statistical metrics and analysis of field structural change**

198 We estimate three aspects - size, density and shape - of fields using the metrics described below,
199 which allow for quantitative measurement of FiSC.

200 *Metrics for field structure*

201 Size of fields: We compute the area of individual field polygons in hectares and square meters.

202 Following this, we aggregate the obtained values at the grid level to get the total agricultural
203 area (hectares) and the median field size (MedFS) of each cell.

204 Field density: This refers to the number of fields in each cell relative to the total agricultural
205 area of the cell. This field per hectare of agricultural area (FA) value provides a normalized
206 value that can be compared between the grid cells.

207

$$208 \quad FA_{i,j} = \frac{N_j}{A_{i,j}} \quad [2.31]$$

209 Where:

210 $FA_{i,j}$ = field density - number of fields per area(ha) in cell j for year i .

211 N_j = total number of fields in cell j for year i .

212 $A_{i,j}$ = total area (in ha) of fields in cell j for year i .

213 Shape of fields: To examine the shape of fields, we assess the complexity of the field shapes
214 using a shape metric known in ecology as the corrected perimeter-area ratio, or SHAPE. This
215 metric was used in a similar study (Brown and Schulte 2011) and is calculated as shown in
216 Equation 2.32 (Baker and Cai 1992).

217

$$218 \quad SHAPE = \frac{0.282 \times p}{\sqrt{a}}$$
$$219 \quad SHAPE \geq 1 \quad [2.32]$$

220 Where:

221 a_f (referred to as a) = area (in m²) of field f .

222 p_f (referred to as p) = perimeter (m) of field f .

223 Typically, SHAPE values increase as the complexity of the shape increases. For example, a
224 long, slim rectangular field will have a higher SHAPE than a more circular field of comparable
225 area, while a well-rounded field will have SHAPE = 1 (Figure 2).

	A	B	C	D
Field				
Area (ha):	1.94	1.93	1.93	0.03
SHAPE:	1.84	1.42	1.20	1.01

226

227 *Figure 2: Three examples of fields with approximately the same area (ha) but different*
 228 *SHAPE values and an approximately circular field. Field A has SHAPE 1.84, indicating its*
 229 *higher shape complexity when compared to Fields B, C, or D, even though Field A's area is*
 230 *comparable to that of Fields B and C.*

231 We use equation 2.32 to calculate SHAPE for each field. Following, we obtain the median
 232 SHAPE value (MedSHAPE) at the cell level for each year in the dataset.

233 Figure 3 illustrates an example of FiSC. In the figure, there are two images: one from 2020 and
 234 the other from 2023. The blue (2020) and yellow (2023) lines represent field polygons, while
 235 the background photographs are digital orthophotos sourced from the OpenGeoData hub of
 236 Lower Saxony (LGLN, 2021). Therefore, we see in these images both the field polygons as
 237 provided by the IACS data and also the land use of the fields as shown by the orthophotos. For
 238 the purpose of illustrating FiSC, the focus is on the polygons.

239

240

Figure 3: An illustration of Field Structural Change between two years.

241 The red-marked area of each image is one administratively recognized contiguous piece of land
 242 in the area. While handy for this illustration, unlike the 10 km² grid cells, administrative land
 243 identifications do not provide comparable land areas for our analysis. In the case of this
 244 illustration, the indicated land area contained two fields in 2020, while the exact location had
 245 three fields in 2023. The average field size in the enclosure was 7.82 ha in 2020, but 4.82 ha in
 246 2023, indicating a decrease in average field size in the area. The average field shape complexity
 247 also changed, though minimally, decreasing from 1.24 in 2020 to 1.20 in 2023, indicating a
 248 simpler field shape in 2023.

249 *Estimating temporal change*

250 For size and shape, we compute the relative differences of cell median values from the baseline
 251 year 2012. As stated in formula 2.33, used for the change of shape and size, we subtract the
 252 median metric of cell j in year i from cell j 's median metric value in 2012, divide by the 2012
 253 value and multiply by 100 to obtain a percentage change or relative difference to 2012.

254

$$255 \quad \text{Change}_{i,j} = \frac{\text{Median}_{i,j} - \text{Median}_{2012,j}}{\text{Median}_{2012,j}} \times 100 \quad [2.33]$$

256 Where:

- 257 • $\text{Change}_{i,j}$: The percentage change for cell j year i .
- 258 • $\text{Median}_{i,j}$: The median size or shape value for cell j year i .
- 259 • $\text{Median}_{2012,j}$: The median metric value of cell j year 2012.

260 We similarly compute the relative differences for the field density metric but without using a
 261 median since FA is already a cell metric.

$$262 \quad \text{ChangeFA}_{i,j} = \frac{\text{FA}_{i,j} - \text{FA}_{2012,j}}{\text{FA}_{2012,j}^{-1}} \times 100 \quad [2.34]$$

263 Using estimates obtained from applying the specified statistical metrics and change formulas,
264 we examine the pattern and spatial distribution of recent developments in field structural change
265 (i.e., RQ1) by visualizing FiSC values across all grid cells using line plots and maps. Having
266 illustrated the temporal pattern of change across all years for all cells and field structure metrics
267 using line plots, we focus our spatial visualization on every fourth year of the study period, i.e.,
268 2016, 2020, and 2024.

269 **2.4. Relating field structural change and farm structural change**

270 We expect field structural change to be associated with farm structural change (Figure 4). A
271 change in average farm size in a district may correlate positively with a change in average field
272 size because increases in farm size, implying larger utilizable agricultural area, could motivate
273 farmers to expand their fields and the extent of expansion could positively relate to the extent
274 of increase in farm size. Although increases in utilizable agricultural area may initially suggest
275 the creation of additional fields, farmers' incentives to optimize field management suggest they
276 are more likely to increase field sizes without increasing field density as farm size increases.
277 Therefore, increases and larger increases in average farm size in a district may not correlate
278 positively with increasing density of fields. Owing to this expected homogeneous-oriented
279 change in field size and density, i.e., larger and not more fields as farm size increases, we also
280 expect that increasing farm size should correlate negatively with change in average shape
281 complexity of fields in a district. The larger farms become, on average, in a district, the larger,
282 less dense and simpler-shaped fields in this district should likely become.

283

284 *Figure 4: Expected correlation between field structural change and farm structural change.*
285 Contrastingly, we expect changes in number of farms in a district to correlate positively with
286 change in density of fields but negatively with change in average size and shape of fields.
287 Ceteris paribus, the same agricultural area in a district will contain more fields as the number
288 of farms in the district increases. Because of the finite resource nature of land, more fields might
289 thus imply the creation of relatively smaller fields with shapes suited to land availability, hence
290 increasing likelihood of irregular shapes.

291 Following estimation of field metrics as described in section 2.3, this section of our study,
292 addressing RQ2, proceeds first with computing the change in number of farms and mean farm
293 size for each district for 2016 and 2020 relative to 2010 using the available farm data. These
294 district values are then mapped to the corresponding grid cells in our field data by merging the
295 cells and districts using the largest overlaps. Given the temporal limitation of farm data
296 compared to field data, in combining the field and farm data, we use the available years of farm
297 data as proxy for the years that are missing in farm data but existing in the field data as follows:
298 2010 farm cross-section as proxy for 2012 to harmonise the baseline year of the field and farm
299 data sets to 2012, 2016 cross-section as cross-section for 2016 and proxy for years 2013 to 2015,
300 and 2020 as cross-section for 2020 and proxy for missing years from 2017 to 2024.

301 The variables of interest for FiSC in the emerging combined field and farm data are change in
302 MedFS, change in FA and change in MedSHAPE. The variables of interest for farm structural
303 change include change in mean farm size and change in the number of farms. While the values
304 of FiSC are estimated and unique at the 10 km² grid-cell level, the values for farm structural
305 change variables are the same across all grid cells within a district.

306 To examine the relationship between the FiSC and farm structural change variables, we explore
307 the case of the changes that occurred in 2020 relative to the baseline year. We estimate the
308 correlation coefficient for each unique field-farm variable pair and plot a scatter matrix to
309 visualize the degree and direction of plausible relationships between the variables. Making two-

310 dimensional scatter plots of variable pairs with district-level farm variables on the horizontal
311 (x) axis and grid-level field variables on the vertical (y) axis implies that, for each district, there
312 is a vertical ordering of the grid cells belonging to that district.

313 Given the clear split and clustering of Lower Saxony's districts by the main crop cultivated in
314 each district (Figure 1), we extend the correlation analysis by disaggregating the data into the
315 four groups of main cultivated crops illustrated in Figure 1. This allows us to detect differences
316 in the relationship between field and farm structural change that may be linked to the district
317 clusters.

318 3. RESULTS

319 3.1 Heterogeneous pattern of field structural change

320 Looking at changes in FiSC metrics over time shows large variations in temporal developments
321 across grid cells (see Figure 5). What also becomes clear is that focusing only on aggregated
322 effects, e.g., the mean change in indicators across grid cells (purple lines in Figure 5), masks
323 important heterogeneity at the individual grid-cell level. For all three indicators, at the
324 aggregated level, we find smaller than $\pm 5\%$ mean change values for MedFS, FA and
325 MedSHAPE in all 12 years. However, with average standard deviation of 6.82, 4.70 and 1.28
326 per year for changes in MedFS, FA and MedSHAPE respectively, the observed extent of change
327 in field structure over time is largely heterogeneous among cells.

328

329 *Figure 5: Line plots of changes in field structural change metrics in Lower Saxony. The plots*
330 *show the change pattern for all three metrics of field size, density and shape of fields across all*
331 *grid cells covering the study area.*

332 Figure 6 provides an overview of the share of cells with increases or decreases in metric values
 333 for 2016, 2020, and 2024 relative to baseline. The largest aggregate increase in MedFS was
 334 1.09%, while the largest aggregate decrease was -3.72% . However, some cells exhibited large
 335 MedFS increases, up to 23% of the 2012 value, while others had declines of up to -46% .
 336 Moving from 60% in 2016 to 29% in 2024, cells exhibiting increases in MedFS became less
 337 common over time, whereas the proportion of cells with declines in MedFS grew (Figure 6).

338

339 *Figure 6: Kernel density plots showing the distribution of cells across metric change values,*
 340 *and the proportion of cells with increases or decreases for 2016, 2020, 2024.*

341 Spatial distribution of the cells (illustrated in Figure 7) reveals regional clustering, with
 342 neighboring cells exhibiting comparable change magnitudes in similar directions (positive or
 343 negative), alongside observable contrasts in the direction of change between the eastern and
 344 western cells.

345 In 2016 and 2020, several clusters of cells with larger MedFS were located in the western part
346 of Lower Saxony. Similar clustering of increasing MedFS occurred in 2024 in the west, but
347 among fewer cells, as several cells had declines in MedFS (Figure 7, row 1, columns 2-4).
348 Important information for drawing conclusions about this result is that this western Lower
349 Saxony, which shows a tendency towards increasing MedFS, contains districts that mainly
350 cultivate forage crops (Figure 1), and several cells with small to moderate MedFS (1.50 ha to
351 2.50 ha) in 2012 (Figure 7, row 1, column 1). Unlike eastern Lower Saxony, where grasslands,
352 cereals, or root crops are mainly cultivated, and where we found more cells with MedFS larger
353 than 2.50 ha in 2012, western districts had only a small number of such cells. In 2020 and 2024,
354 there was a strong eastern clustering of cells with high MedFS decreases. This pattern of
355 declining MedFS similarly prevailed in the east in 2016, but among fewer cells. As a result of
356 these changes across the study area over time, the proportion of cells with large MedFS shifted
357 between 2012 and 2024. 48% of the 501 cells covering the districts of Lower Saxony had
358 moderate to large MedFS of 2 ha or above in 2012. By 2024, this proportion of cells had
359 decreased by 9 percentage points, resulting in an increase in the proportion of cells with less
360 than 2 ha MedFS to 61% (Table A.1).

361 Change in FA relative to 2012 exhibited an aggregate declining pattern ranging from -0.88% to
362 -3.09%. However, cell-level examination exposes cells with years of increases of up to +25%
363 which, in absolute terms, is larger than the largest observed decrease of -17%. Cells with
364 positive FA change became more common between 2016 and 2024, moving from 20% to 42%.
365 Correspondingly, the proportion of cells with negative FA changes dropped (Figure 6). In 2016,
366 decrease in FA occurred in cells spatially distributed across all regions of Lower Saxony.
367 However, cells with increase in FA were found to be located more in the east. A similar spatial
368 distribution was observed in 2020, but with higher intensity of decrease and increase values,
369 and a greater presence of cells with increase in FA in the east. In 2024, the presence of cells

370 with increase in FA extended to the west, reducing the proportion of cells with decrease in FA
 371 across Lower Saxony (Figure 7, row 2, columns 2-4). Unlike the 2.0 ha MedFS breakpoint,
 372 there was no FA value beyond or below which proportion of cells consistently increased or
 373 decreased in 2024 as compared to 2012. Instead, the proportion of cells randomly changed
 374 between the multiple discrete intervals FA (Table A.1).

375 *Figure 7¹: Maps of actual field structure metric values for each 10km² cell in the baseline*
 376 *(2012) and final year (2024) of study as well as maps showing the changes in cell values for*
 377 *2016, 2020 and 2024 relative to 2012.*

378 The spatial distribution observed in the pattern of change in density of fields (or number of
 379 fields per agricultural area) was inversely similar to that observed for the change in average
 380 field size. But, unlike with average field size, the increases and decreases in field density were

¹ For each metric (row) in Figure 7, the same bin ranges were applied to the 2012 and 2024 actual value maps to enable direct comparison of value distributions. Similarly, the same bin ranges were applied to all change maps.

381 more randomly distributed across space. The observed pattern of increase in the number of
382 fields per area in districts where average field size decreased indicates that these processes are
383 simultaneous: fields become smaller as the number of fields increases in a given area.

384 Aggregately, MedSHAPE exhibited a steadily increasing trend over time, with only 2013
385 having an approximately zero but negative aggregate change. At the cell level, we observe up
386 to -7% decline and increase in shape complexity as large as $+13\%$ increase relative to 2012.
387 From 2016 to 2024, the proportion of cells with an increase in MedSHAPE increased (Figure
388 6), while cells with decreases in MedSHAPE thinned out. Spatially, the direction of
389 MedSHAPE changes was randomly distributed among cells (Figure 7, row 3, columns 2-4).
390 However, cells situated in border areas, such as those near the North Sea coast, predominantly
391 increased over time at notably stronger rates. Ultimately, although only 32% of the 501 cells
392 spanning the districts of Lower Saxony had a MedSHAPE of less than 1.30 in 2012, this
393 proportion decreased by eighteen percentage points in 2024, increasing the proportion of cells
394 with a complexity of 1.30 or more to 86% (Table A.1).

395 **3.2 Relationship between field structural change and farm structural change**

396 Across Lower Saxony, the average size of farms increased in 2020 relative to 2010 while the
397 number of farms declined over time (Figure B.1). When all districts are considered, at an
398 aggregated level changes in average farm size correlate² positively ($r = 0.37$) with changes in
399 MedFS, but negatively with FA changes ($r = -0.28$) and negligibly with MedSHAPE
400 changes ($r = -0.07$). This means that, as expected, an increase in farm size appears together
401 with the expansion of fields but not necessarily an increase in the number of fields. Changes in
402 number of farms correlate negatively ($r = -0.39$) with observed changes in MedFS, but
403 positively with FA changes ($r = 0.31$) and negligibly with MedSHAPE changes ($r = 0.08$). This

² For the relationships described, we explore the case of the changes that occurred in 2020 (the last year in the farm data) relative to the first years i.e., 2010 in the case of farm data and 2012 in the case of field data.

404 agrees with the hypothesis that an increase in the number of farms will occur with an increase
405 in the number of fields, but given the resource constraints on the available agricultural land in
406 a district, these increases will imply smaller average field sizes.

407 Although we observe these overall trends, we find that there is spatial heterogeneity in these
408 relations. Specifically, we find that when districts are grouped based on their main cultivated
409 crop, differences emerge in the relationship between field and farm structural change. The
410 observed overall positive correlation between changes in average farm size and MedFS changes
411 applies for districts that mainly cultivate forage crops and grassland. However, a negative
412 correlation is observed in cereal-cultivating districts (Figure 8). Similarly, the negative
413 correlation between changes in average farm size and FA changes in the overall data is evident
414 in districts cultivating forages and grasslands, but a positive relationship is observed in cereal-
415 cultivating districts. For MedSHAPE change, the correlation with change in farm size becomes
416 less negligible in districts mainly cultivating cereals and forages, with the relationship
417 becoming positive ($\rho = 0.36$) in the former and negative ($\rho = -0.3$) in the latter. See Table
418 A.2 for the correlation coefficients for all district groups.

419 The overall negative correlation between changes in the number of farms and changes in MedFS
420 holds for districts that mainly cultivate forage crops and grassland. However, a positive
421 correlation is observed in cereal-cultivating districts (Figure 8). Similarly, the positive
422 correlation between changes in the number of farms and FA changes in the overall data persists
423 in districts cultivating forages and grasslands, but a negative relationship is observed in cereal-
424 cultivating districts. Similar to change in average farm size and MedSHAPE changes, the
425 correlation between changes in the number of farms and changes in MedSHAPE becomes less
426 negligible in districts mainly cultivating cereals ($r = -0.37$) and forages ($r = 0.38$).

427

428

429 *Figure 8: Scatterplots with trend line³ showing the associations between the change values of*
 430 *field structure metrics (median field size, density of fields and median shape complexity) and*
 431 *farm structure variables (median farm size and number of farms) for all 501 cells of the study*
 432 *area.*

³ The different colours in the scatterplots show districts where i) cereals are mainly cultivated, ii) forage crops are the main cultivated crops, iii) grasslands are the main cultivated crops and iv) regions where root crops dominate. In all plots, some of the data points align vertically due to the technique used to combine the field and farm data. While field data is at the 10km² grid level, the farm data is at the NUTS3 regional level but mapped to corresponding grid cells. Thus, all points represent individual grid cells, but although there is a spread in the FiSC values of these cells, the farm structural change values for cells within the same districts are the same. In the plots, points for cells cultivating root crops can hardly be seen, as these constitute only one district.

433 **4. DISCUSSION**

434 Our first research question enquired about the medium-term pattern of field structural change
435 and how the patterns may compare spatially. Demonstrated by high heterogeneity in the
436 magnitudes and patterns of baseline-relative changes in field structure across the multiple years
437 and areas examined, our findings suggest that medium-term changes in field structure can be
438 expected to vary between the years, as well as between finer-scale locations within regions of
439 interest. Suggesting that this observation may also apply to long-term changes, Skaloš et al.
440 (2012) similarly observed periodic variations in field sizes between 1703 and 2006 in Swedish
441 and East Bohemian study sites. Overall, there is limited existing evidence for temporal analysis
442 of field structural change, and existing studies tend to focus on very specific locations. From a
443 4km² area of Saxony-Anhalt, Germany, Baessler & Klotz (2006) reported a decline in the
444 number of fields between 1953 -2000, an increase in mean patch size and a decrease in field
445 shape complexity. Similarly, Brown and Schulte (2011) found that field size and shape
446 complexity increased while the number of farm fields decreased between 1937 and 2002 in
447 three Iowa towns.

448 Based on our findings of the largest cluster of cells with increasing average field size and
449 decreasing density of fields in western Lower Saxony, where forage crop is mainly cultivated,
450 as well as the characteristically small field sizes the south, where cereals are mainly cultivated,
451 we speculate that heterogeneity of field structure and field structural change may be related to
452 differences in crop cultivation and farming specialization. Examining two different countries
453 but still relatively small areas therein, Skaloš et al. (2012) attribute variations in the pattern of
454 field structure change to land reforms that supported the consolidation of arable land,
455 collectivization, and redistribution of land plots at different points in time. However, these
456 aspect are not relevant drivers in the median time perspective we considere.

457 Pertaining to our second research question on the relationship between field structural change
458 and farm structural change, the observed dissimilar relationship in the cereal-cultivating

459 districts contradicts our expectation of a positive correlation, as known for actual field and
460 actual farm size (Levin 2006; Noack et al. 2022; Jänicke et al. 2024). An assumed explanation
461 for this is the concentration of these cereal-cultivating districts in the south of Lower Saxony,
462 near the Harz Mountains, and thus the speculation of an impact of high elevation on field
463 structural change. The marginal land condition characteristic (Csikós & Tóth, 2023) of high-
464 elevation areas may limit the extent of productive land area and constrain the extent to which
465 field sizes can increase. This explanation is consistent with our examination of the association
466 between field structural change and elevation, which shows that districts with higher mean
467 elevation are more likely to experience decreases in average field size (Figure B.2).

468 Although causal evidence of institutional or political and other determinants of field structural
469 change remains an open question for potential future exploration, evidence from this study
470 already points towards how policies may lead to changes in field structures. The decline of
471 farms in all districts of Lower Saxony between 2010 and 2020, consistent with the trend of
472 fewer farms in the EU (Neuenfeldt et al., 2019), hints that the increases in the number of fields
473 and decreases in average field sizes in the relevant districts may have been driven by other
474 determinants beyond simple farm structural change decisions. An interesting perspective that
475 remains unexplored is the extent to which EU agricultural sustainability-targeted policies and
476 associated landscape-oriented strategies determine changes in field structures. For example, the
477 biodiversity strategies of the European Green Deal (EGD) and the Common Agricultural Policy
478 (CAP) include regulations that address the proportion of landscape features or grasslands on
479 farmlands (Cortignani et al., 2017; Müller et al., 2025). These regulations, which may require
480 farms to modify arable fields to accommodate more ecologically friendly fields, may lead to an
481 increase in the number of fields and smaller average field sizes, regardless of occurring change
482 in size and number of farms in the areas and districts where farmers make these modifications.
483 Although these policies are implemented state-wide, an open question for further research is to

484 what extent spatial heterogeneity in field structures can be explained by heterogeneous
485 responses of farms to these policies.

486 The predominant pattern of increasing field shape complexity across the districts of Lower
487 Saxony suggests the introduction of more irregularly shaped fields over time in the districts.
488 Given that regular fields are considered more efficient due to the economies of scale in field
489 management processes, such as the use of large machinery (Janulevičius & Čiplienė, 2018;
490 Nilsson & Rosenqvist, 2021; Spekken et al., 2015), it is economically counterintuitive for
491 farmers to make their fields less regular. However, making fields smaller or setting aside small
492 field areas for landscape elements, such as buffer and flower strips can improve ecological
493 outcomes (Clough et al., 2020) and increase the average complexity of field shapes over time.
494 We observed this in our study, as change in shape complexity was found to be negatively
495 correlated with change in average field size, but positively correlated with change in number of
496 fields per area. Creating smaller fields based on ecological rationales and thereby increasing
497 average field shape complexity would also support the hypothesis that biodiversity or
498 landscape-sustainability strategies may influence changes in field structure.

499 Summarily, this study crucially establishes that field structural change can be heterogeneous
500 across temporal and spatial scales. It highlights that evidence of field structural change from a
501 small site may have low external validity, and the transferability of derived expectations to
502 other locations cannot be relied upon unless local characteristics that may create similarity in
503 expectations can be identified, e.g., whether the area to be extrapolated to is in the same western
504 or eastern region, typically cultivates the same crops, has similar topography or farmers
505 similarly interact with political and institutional environments. Therefore, policies and
506 institutional strategies such as the German agri-environmental measure, which specifies size
507 caps for arable fields (RECHT.NRW.DE 2022) in order to manage trajectories of landscapes
508 and their sustainability outcomes, may benefit from spatially extensive analyses similar to that

509 demonstrated in this study. Such spatially extensive analysis will help understand the prevailing
510 patterns and influential drivers of field structural change across different locations, rather than
511 in single or a few small locations. When conducted before strategy formulation and
512 implementation, these extensive studies can improve targeting and align strategies with local
513 farm and field conditions.

514 This study leveraged IACS parcel-level data, enabling a spatially extensive analysis without the
515 labour- and time-consuming aerial data processing steps, such as digitization, that were
516 necessary in earlier studies of field structural change and thus pose spatial coverage limitations.
517 Spanning up to 17 years in some EU member states (Jänicke et al., 2025), the availability of
518 IACS data in several EU regions provides the possibility for replication of this study for local
519 understanding of field structural change for improving related agricultural and landscape
520 sustainability policies in the EU. Although available, member states often lack clearly defined
521 portals that provide public access to this data for all existing years across all regions covered
522 by IACS within the states. Rather, access varies between country regions, e.g., between the
523 federal states of Germany. However, there are ongoing efforts to harmonize access and the
524 structure of the IACS data for improved accessibility in the future (Jänicke et al., 2025).
525 Harmonized structure and access to IACS data across EU member states and regions within
526 countries ease the scaling of spatial studies, such as field structural change, to larger spatial
527 extents.

528

529 **5. CONCLUSION**

530 This spatio-temporal study of field structural change (FiSC) in every agriculturally productive
531 10 km² area of Lower Saxony offers spatially explicit evidence of changes in field size, shape,
532 and density over the last 13 years, while also relating these to farm structural changes in the
533 study area. The primary role of fields in agricultural production implies that studying how field
534 structures change is relevant for understanding landscape outcomes over time and for
535 potentially improving the environmental sustainability of agricultural production. Our findings
536 highlight the variable dynamics of agricultural production across larger areas, such as federal
537 states, in which expected changes in field structure can be temporally and spatially
538 heterogeneous and may not follow farm structural changes as might be presumed. The variable
539 temporal changes suggest that evidence of recent and medium-term changes in field structure,
540 rather than that from distant time periods, may provide a more time-relevant background for
541 the formulation of agricultural and landscape sustainability strategies. Further, the spatial
542 variations suggest that farm and field structures are not necessarily changing similarly or in a
543 manner consistent with expectations, across large spatial extents or between districts with
544 different crop specializations. It is therefore perhaps beneficial for policymakers to be cautious
545 when applying evidence of field or farm structural change from certain locations to formulate
546 regulations for other locations, even within the same larger political regions. Given the non-
547 inferential nature of this study, the suggested associations between FiSC and crop specialization,
548 as well as between FiSC and agricultural sustainability policies, highlight opportunities for
549 causal investigation into how these and other economic factors related to agricultural production
550 actually motivate and influence FiSC.

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562 **Conflicts of interest/ Competing interests**

563 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
564 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

565 **Ethics approval/ Consent to participate/Consent for publication**

566 Not applicable to this article as no human participants involved during the current study.

567 **Availability of data and material**

568 Possibility of publication of the complete data is still under review.

569 **Authors' contributions**

570 D. T. A.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing- Original draft
571 preparation, Visualization. J. B.: Software validation. C. W: Writing- Reviewing and Editing.
572 T. K.: Supervision, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. H. S.: Supervision, Writing- Reviewing
573 and Editing, Funding acquisition.

574

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		Proportion of 10 km ² grid cells (%)		
Metric	Range (ha)	2012	2024	Difference
Median field size (MedFS)	0.80 - 1.50	15.17%	19.8%	4.6%
	1.50 - 2.00	36.33%	40.7%	4.4%
	2.00 - 2.50	35.73%	30.7%	-5.0%
	2.50 - 3.50	11.78%	8.4%	-3.4%
	3.50 - 4.30	1.00%	0.4%	-0.6%
Density of fields (FA)	0.00 - 0.29	17.37%	19.96%	2.6%
	0.29 - 0.33	21.76%	20.36%	-1.4%
	0.33 - 0.37	21.36%	23.35%	2.0%
	0.37 - 0.43	18.76%	16.37%	-2.4%
	0.43 - 1.00	20.76%	19.96%	-0.8%
Median field shape (MedSHAPE)	1.00 - 1.30	32.46%	14.03%	-18.4%
	1.30 - 1.35	49.50%	56.71%	7.2%
	1.35 - 1.40	10.82%	19.04%	8.2%
	1.40 - 1.50	4.81%	7.01%	2.2%
	1.50 - 2.00	2.40%	3.21%	0.8%

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Table A.2: Correlation coefficients of all districts and for district subsets by main cultivated crop groups

	Districts Subset by Main Cultivated Crops	Farm Structural Change i.e., % Change in		
		Mean farm size	Number of farms	
Field Structural Change i.e., % Change in	Median field size (MedFS)		0.37	-0.39
		Cereals	-0.34	0.35
		Forage crops	0.55	-0.55
		Grasslands	0.36	-0.39
	Density of fields (FA)		-0.28	0.31
		Cereals	0.30	-0.30
		Forage crops	-0.42	0.51
		Grasslands	-0.20	0.20
	Median field shape (MedSHAPE)		-0.07	0.08
		Cereals	0.36	-0.37
		Forage crops	-0.33	0.38
Grasslands		0.05	-0.07	

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683

Appendix B: Supplementary Figures

684

685 *Figure B.1: Percentage change in farm structure variables in year 2020 relative to 2010. a) Change in*
686 *mean farm size b) change in total number of farms.*

687

688

689 *Figure B.2: a) Elevation map of Lower Saxony. Data source: Copernicus Global Digital*
690 *(GLO-30), obtained using Google Earth Engine. b, c, d) Scatterplots relating mean elevation to*
691 *average changes in field size, density and shape. Data for elevation and field structural change*
692 *metrics are at the 10 km² cell levels, and the change metric values are averaged across 2013 to 2024*
693 *for each cell.*